

Adaptation Factor Analysis Instrument of Interpersonal Support Evaluation List in Indonesian Version: Confirmatory Approach

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ABSTRACT: Social support is an interpersonal transaction that involves one or more things such as emotional attention, instrumental assistance, information, and appraisal. Social support comes from the perception that there are people who will help if a situation or event that is considered to cause a problem occurs, and this help is believed to increase positive feelings and self-esteem. Social support has 4 functions; tangible support, appraisal support, self-esteem support, and belonging support (Cohen & Hoberman, 1983). The interpersonal support evaluation list (ISEL) is a social support measurement instrument widely used in various countries. Using instruments in different cultural backgrounds requires adaptation processes to be valid and reliable with the respondents being tested. However, until now there has been no research on the adaptation of ISEL measuring instruments in Indonesia. This research aims to obtain a standardized Indonesian version of the ISEL measuring instrument. The adaptation process was calculated using the International Test Commission reference (Commission, 2017). Based on the results of the CFA analysis with the JASP 0.18.3.0 program, it can be concluded that according to theory, the Indonesian version of the ISEL instrument has proven valid and reliable in measuring social support in the Indonesian adolescent population.

KEYWORDS: Adaptation, Confirmatory Factor Analysis, Interpersonal Support Evaluation List, Social Support.

INTRODUCTION

Various definitions of social support are described in previous studies. According to Caplan (1983), the function of social support is (1) providing individuals with information and guidance to solve and overcome stressful daily problems, (2) providing attention, affection, and protection which will shape and support self-esteem and create a sense of self-confidence, and (3) encourage and assess the individual's ability to overcome stressful situations and provide a supportive evaluation of the work carried out (Riston, 2020). Cobb (1976) defines social support as information that makes the subject believe that he is cared for and loved, appreciated and has a communication network and mutual obligations (Mahmuda & Jalal, 2022). House (1981) suggests that social support is an interpersonal transaction involving one or more of the following: (1) emotional attention (like, love, empathy), (2) instrumental assistance (goods or services), (3) information (about the environment), and (4) appraisal (information relevant to self-evaluation) (Utami & Wijaya, 2018). According to Cohen & Hoberman (1983), social support refers to the various resources provided by a person's interpersonal relationships. Social support has a positive effect on health, which may be visible even when not under great stress (Cohen et al., 2000). Cohen and Wills (1985) define social support as the help and support a person obtains from interactions with others. Social support arises from the perception that there are people who will help if a situation or event that causes problems occurs and it is felt to increase positive feelings and raise self-esteem. (Rossiter & Sochos, 2018).

Several previous studies provide the background of why the Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL) is considered the best measuring tool currently for measuring social support. Dunkel-Schetter, et al (1987) researched psychological problems related to receiving social support and examined a study on stress from 150 middle-aged people. All research subjects were interviewed every month for 6 months regarding the stressful situations they faced through the previous month. Social support received and various coping methods applied are also assessed over time, as are other variables. The hypothesized factors are related to the likelihood of support received by each person, appraisal patterns related to specific stressors, and coping strategies. However, each factor tends to be more strongly related to a certain type of social support. A person's predispositions are strongly related to emotional support, appraisal factors are strongly related to help, and coping strategies are strongly related to informational support. (Dunkel-Schetter et al., 1987).

According to (Taylor & Brown, 1988), many leading experts have provided opinions about accurate perception of oneself, the world, and the future which is essential for mental health. However, there are research evidences showing that positive self-evaluations,

exaggerated perceptions of control, and unrealistic optimism are characteristics of normal human thinking. Additionally, these illusions appear to promote mental health criteria, including the ability to care about others, the ability to be happy or content, and the ability to engage in productive and creative work. These strategies may be successful in most people because the social world and cognitive processing provide filters for incoming information to be filtered in a positive direction; Negative information can be isolated and presented in a non-threatening way. These positive illusions may be useful when an individual receives negative or threatening feedback and may be highly adaptive.

Several social support measuring tools are based on different indicators. Some of them are as follows:

Table 1. The Development of Social Support Measuring Tools

No.	Name of Measuring Instrument	Compiler	Description of Measuring Tools
1.	Social Support Questionnaire	(Irwin G. Sarason et al., 1983)	The questionnaire contains 27 items designed to measure perceptions of social support and satisfaction with that social support. Each item is a question that requires a two-part answer: Part 1 asks participants to list all the people who fit the question description, and Part 2 asks participants to indicate how satisfied they are, in general, with these people.
2.	Social Support Questionnaire - shortened version	(I. G. Sarason et al., 1987)	A 6-item questionnaire designed to measure social support. Each item is a question that requires a two-part response: Part 1 asks participants to list all the people who fit the question description, and part 2 asks participants to indicate how satisfied they are, in general, with those people.
3.	Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL)	(Cohen & Hoberman, 1983)	A 40-item scale consists of four subscales. The subscales are: 1) Real Support 2) Proprietary Support 3) Self-Esteem Support 4) Assessment Support Participants rate each statement item based on the truth or falsity of their self-beliefs. All answers are given on a 4-point scale ranging from "Definitely True" to "Must be Wrong."
4.	Interpersonal Support Evaluation List - shortened version	(Cohen et al., 1985)	A 12-item measure of perception of social support. This questionnaire has three different subscales designed to measure three dimensions of perceived social support, namely: 1) Assessment Support 2) Proprietary Support 3) Real Support Each dimension is measured with 4 items on a 4-point scale ranging from "Definitely True" to "Definitely False".

The interpersonal support evaluation list is designed to assess the perceived availability of support from the four social support functions as well as provide overall support measures. Four dimensions of social support function based on Cohen & McKay's (1984) theory, namely: (1) tangible support, which is intended to measure the perceived availability of material assistance; (2) appraisal support, which is intended to measure a person's perceived availability to talk to about one's problems; (3) self-esteem support, which is intended to measure the perceived availability of positive comparisons when comparing oneself with others; and (4) belonging support, which is intended to measure the availability that people feel they can use to do something (Cohen & McKay, 2020). Based on the social support measuring tools above, the researcher decided to choose an interpersonal support evaluation instrument with a list of 40 items. This is because this instrument is considered to be able to describe in more detail research samples with cultural backgrounds in Indonesia later.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research procedures

This research aims to test a tool for measuring social support among teenagers from 12 - 23 years by involving the functional dimensions of tangible support, appraisal support, self-esteem support, and belonging support.

Table 2. The Dimensions of Social Support

No.	Dimension	Dimensional interpretation
1.	Tangible support	Refers to the perception of the availability of material assistance.
2.	Appraisal support	Refers to the perception of someone's availability to talk to about problems
3.	Self-esteem support	Refers to the perception of positive comparisons when comparing oneself with others
4.	Belonging Support	Refers to the perception of the availability of people who can do something together.

The measuring tool that was used in this research is the Interpersonal Support Evaluation List 40 (ISEL) which was developed by (Cohen & Hoberman, 1983). This research is quantitative research with the type of ex-facto research. This research involved teenagers who met the respondent criteria and were willing to fill out an online questionnaire and be included in the sample for this research. The respondents that were sampled in this study are teenagers with an age range of 12 - 23 years and live in Indonesia. The data was collected using an online questionnaire in the form of a Google form and distributed online via social media. Based on the results, 58 teenagers were obtained to become respondents in this research.

Table 3. Instrument Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL 40)

No.	Social Support Function	Instrument Serial Number	Statement	Scored
1.	Tangible Support	2	If I needed help fixing an appliance or repairing my car, there is someone who would help me.	Real
		9	If I needed a ride to the airport very early in the morning, I would have a hard time finding someone to take me.	Reverse scored
		14	If I were sick and needed someone (friend, family member, or acquaintance) to take me to the doctor, I would have trouble finding someone.	Reverse scored

		16	If I needed a place to stay for a week because of an emergency (for example, water or electricity out in my apartment or house), I could easily find someone who would put me up.	Real
		18	If I were sick, I could easily find someone to help me with my daily chores.	Real
		23	If I needed an emergency loan of \$100, there is someone (friend, relative, or acquaintance) I could get it from.	
		29	If I had to go out of town for a few weeks, it would be difficult to find someone who would look after my house or apartment (the plants, pets, garden, etc.).	Reverse scored
		33	If I was stranded 10 miles from home, there is someone I could call who would come and get me.	Real
		35	It would me difficult to find someone who would lend me their car for a few hours.	Reverse scored
		39	If I needed some help in moving to a new house or apartment, I would have a hard time finding someone to help me.	Reverse scored
2.	Appraisal Support	1	There are several people that I trust to help solve my problems.	Real
		6	I often meet or talk with family or friends.	Reverse scored
		11	There really is no one who can give me an objective view of how I'm handling my problems.	Reverse scored
		17	I feel that there is no one I can share my most private worries and fears with.	Reverse scored
		19	There is someone I can turn to for advice about handling problems with my family.	Real
		22	When I need suggestions on how to deal with a personal problem, I know someone I can turn to.	Real
		26	There is someone I could turn to for advice about making career plans or changing my job.	Real
		30	There really is no one I can trust to give me good financial advice.	Reverse scored
		36	If a family crisis arose, it would be difficult to find someone who could give me good advice about how to handle it.	Reverse scored
		38	There is at least one person I know whose advice I really trust.	Real
3.	Self-Esteem Support	3	Most of my friends are more interesting than I am.	Reverse scored
		4	There is someone who takes pride in my accomplishments.	Real
		8	Most people I know think highly of me.	Real
		13	I think that my friends feel that I'm not very good at helping them solve their problems.	Reverse scored
		20	I am as good at doing things as most other people are.	Real
		24	In general, people do not have much confidence in me.	Reverse scored
		28	Most of my friends are more successful at making changes in their lives than I am.	Reverse scored
		32	I am more satisfied with my life than most people are with theirs.	Real
		37	I am closer to my friends than most other people are to theirs.	Real
		40	I have a hard time keeping pace with my friends.	Reverse scored

4.	Belonging Support	5	When I feel lonely, there are several people I can talk to.	Real
		7	I often meet or talk with family or friends.	Real
		10	I feel like I'm not always included by my circle of friends.	Reverse scored
		12	There are several different people I enjoy spending time with.	Real
		15	If I wanted to go on a trip for a day (e.g., to the mountains, beach, or country), I would have a hard time finding someone to go with me.	Reverse scored
		21	If I decide one afternoon that I would like to go to a movie that evening, I could easily find someone to go with me.	Real
		25	Most people I know do not enjoy the same things that I do.	Reverse scored
		27	I don't often get invited to do things with others.	Reverse scored
		31	If I wanted to have lunch with someone, I could easily find someone to join me.	Real
		34	No one I know would throw a birthday party for me.	Reverse scored

Guidelines for translating and adapting the instruments used in this research were prepared by the International Test Commission (ITC) second edition (Commission, 2017). The steps that were taken in adapting the measuring instrument in this research are as follows:

The 1st stage is the **pre-condition** stage. At this stage, the researchers contacted the first author, Prof. Sheldon Cohen to ask permission to adapt the interpersonal support evaluation list measuring tool into Indonesian by email. The original format of the instrument was obtained from a published article in the Journal of Applied Social Psychology in 1983. Next, the researchers assess item construction and suitability for the population of interest in the research, and familiarity with the administration of the measuring instrument (instructions and rating scales) in identifying cultural characteristics, and irrelevant language.

The 2nd stage is the **test development** stage. In this second stage, the researchers translated the interpersonal support evaluation list (ISEL 40) instrument from English to Indonesian using the Indonesian cultural context. The first translation stage was carried out by translating each item into Indonesian. This translation was carried out by two translators who came from a sworn translation services bureau, were unfamiliar with the construct of social support instruments, graduated in English literature, had TOEFL scores above 500, and were members of the Indonesian Translators Association (HPI).

The 3rd stage is the **synthesis stage of the translation results**. At this stage, the researchers examined the translation results to see possible discrepancies between the two translation results. After that, a back-translation process was carried out from Indonesian to English to see how far the adapted items matched the original items.

The 4th stage is **reviewing the translation results**. At this stage, the synthesis results were given to psychology faculty lecturers with doctoral degrees in applied psychology at Jakarta State University for expert review / expert judgment. The selected experts are expert who has the ability and deep knowledge of psychology. The results of items that have gone through the expert review stage will be included.

Diagram 1. Flow of Adaptation of the Intrapersonal Support Evaluation List Instrument (ISEL 40)

The 5th stage is a **readability test**. A readability test was carried out on the final items. The readability test was given to five teenagers living in the Jakarta area. This was done to ensure all items were understood by participants. From the readability test,

suggestions were obtained to change the nominal value of money from US\$ to Indonesian Rupiah in item so that it could be better understood.

The 6th stage is the administration of measuring instruments. At this stage, the researchers compiled the items into a questionnaire then distributed and asked participants who met the criteria to fill it through social media.

The 7th stage is the analysis of the results. At this stage, the researchers carried out an analysis of the data that had been collected. The analysis was using the Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) approach. The data entered came from 58 participants, however, because 5 participants' data was incomplete, it was declared invalid and only 53 participants' data was subsequently analyzed.

Data analysis in this research was carried out with the help of JASP software

Hoper (2008) states that Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) uses a model fit index that functions as a guide to avoid errors in confirmatory factor results, including:

- a. Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) / absolute fit index that describes the tendency of chi-square to reject a model with a large number of samples (Ilmiah et al., 2023). A good RMSEA fit index is in the range of 0.05-0.08.
- c. Comparative Fit Index (CFI) is an incremental fit index that is relatively insensitive to the size of a sample and the complexity of the model. A good CFI fit index value is >0.90 (Braeken & Laar, 2021).
- d. Incremental Fit Index (IFI) is an index that explains the simplicity of a model and the sample size used (Anggorowati et al., 2019). An index value close to ≥ 0.90 indicates that this model is fit (Simanjuntak & Hamimi, 2019).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pilot Testing and Cognitive Debriefing

A trial of the adapted interpersonal support evaluation list instrument was carried out on 5 participants who were asked to complete the entire research questionnaire via Google Forms and then communicate using Zoom to talk about their experiences in filling out the questionnaire. Researchers asked participants to record the start time and finish time of the work, it was found that the average was 10.3 minutes, so it was decided that in the informed consent, the estimated duration for filling out 40 questionnaires was 10-15 minutes. Next, specifically for the ISEL questionnaire, participants were asked to note down question items that were confusing or difficult to understand, resulting in items number 9, 14, 15, 23, 29, and 33. During the discussion process, the researcher also asked for feedback regarding the clarity of work instructions, the standard appearance of the questionnaire online, and the frequency that is thought about when choosing an answer option. The results of this cognitive debriefing were used as consideration for finalizing the Indonesian version of the ISEL measuring instrument items.

Data Descriptions

After testing and conducting a final review, the questionnaire was distributed online and distributed via social media. 58 respondents' answers were obtained, however, 5 respondents' answers were dropped out because they did not match the age range of teenagers. Based on the frequency distribution test, the data obtained was that 39.6% (21 people) of the sample were male, and 60.4% (32 people) of the sample were female. Based on age, the samples obtained were 14 years old 1.9% (1 person), 15 years old 13.2% (7 people), 16 years old 34% (18 people), 17 years old 13.2% (7 people), 18 years 5.7% (3 people), 19 years 7.5% (4 people), 20 years 13.2% (7 people), 21 years 7.5% (4 people), and 22 years 3.8% (2 persons). Based on academic/educational level, the sample of high school students was 62.3% (33 people), and 37.7% (20 people) were students. Based on ethnicity, the largest sample was obtained from the Javanese tribe, 28.3% (15 people), and the rest was divided into several other tribes. Based on the religion adhered to, the largest sample obtained was Muslim at 41.5% (22 people), followed by Christianity at 39.6% (21 people), and the rest was divided into other religions. Based on marital status, it is known that 3.8% of teenagers in this study were married and 96.2% (51 people) were still single.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Image 1. Initial plot model

Factor analysis was carried out using a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) approach with the Diagonally Weighted Least Square (DWLS) model estimation method. The CFA model with 4 indicators as in this study provides bias that tends to be greater than the 8-indicator model. The DWLS model is used because it can provide consistent results with little bias across different response category values and sample sizes. This approach was chosen to see whether the data from the Indonesian Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL 40) measuring instrument to know whether or nor are following the original theory developed by (Cohen & Hoberman, 1983) which has 4 latent factors. In general, the model produced in Figure 1 is fit (RMSEA=0.071<0.08) so researchers do not need to modify the indices. Table 4 shows the results of the Goodness of Fit Interpersonal Support Evaluation List instrument.

Table 4. Results of the initial 40-item ISEL Goodness of Fit Instrument

No.	Statistic	Criteria	Hasil Perhitungan	Keterangan
1.	X ²		926,118	
2.	df		734	
3.	Chi square P-Value	> 0,05	0,001	Tidak fit
4.	Goodness of fit index (GFI)	≥ 0,90	0,839	Tidak fit
5.	Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	≤ 0,08	0,071	Fit
6.	Comparative fit index (CFI)	≥ 0,9	0,931	Fit
7.	Bentler-Bonnet Non-normed Fit Index (NNFI)	≥ 0,9	0,927	Fit
8.	Incremental fit index (IFI)	≥ 0,9	1,002	Fit

Based on the results obtained, there were still models that were not fit, so the researchers modified the model to obtain a better model. Model modification was carried out by deleting several items that had factor loadings below 0.50. There are two stages in modifying the model. First, this was done by deleting items that have a factor loading below 0.5 (Hair et al., 2014). Hal ini dilakukan karena factor loading This was done because of loading factor. After deleting several items, the following results were obtained:

Image 2. Final plot model

Table 5. Final 40 item ISEL Goodness of Fit Instrument results

No.	Statistic	Criteria	Hasil Perhitungan	Keterangan
1.	X ²		320,202	
2.	df		344	
3.	Chi square P-Value	> 0,05	0,817	Fit
4.	Goodness of fit index (GFI)	≥ 0,90	0,919	Fit
5.	Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	≤ 0,08	0,000	Fit
6.	Comparative fit index (CFI)	≥ 0,90	1,103	Fit
7.	Bentler-Bonnet Non-normed Fit Index (NNFI)	≥ 0,90	1,000	Fit
8.	Incremental fit index (IFI)	≥ 0,90	0,933	Fit

A chi-square test result with a p-value > 0.05 indicates that the model is fit to describe social support. This is also proven by the fit index value which is ≥ 0.000, as in the RMSEA output which is good if the value is ≤ 0.08. This model meets the requirements. The GFI value is also ≥ 0.90. It can be seen that almost all areas have GFI, CFI, IFI, NNFI, and RMSEA values that meet the fit criteria. This means that the interpersonal support evaluation list questionnaire measuring tool can describe the construct being measured. So, it can be concluded that the model used is suitable for describing social support.

Reliability

Reliability analysis of the ISEL dimensions was processed using JASP. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach's alpha. Reliability coefficients range from 0-1 (Hair et al., 2014). The following are the specified reliability criteria.

Table 6. Cronbach's Alpha Reliability Coefficient Category (Heir et al, 2010)

Nilai	Criteria
< 200	Not reliable
0,200 - 0,400	Less reliable
0,400 - 0,700	Quite reliable
0,700 - 0,900	Reliable
>900	Very reliable

Based on the reliability criteria above, the results of the reliability analysis of the 4 interpersonal support evaluation list dimensions can be seen in the table below.

Table 7. Reliability

	Coefficient ω	Coefficient α	Keterangan
Tangible	0.774	0.793	Reliable
Appraisal	0.824	0.810	Reliable
Self-esteem	0.722	0.704	Reliable
Belonging	0.726	0.761	Reliable
Total keseluruhan	0.933	0.923	Very reliable

CONCLUSION

This research aims to validate the adaptation of the Interpersonal Support Evaluation List (ISEL 40 item) measuring tool into the Indonesian version. Based on the results of the CFA analysis, it is known that ISEL 40 has 4 dimensions, namely tangible support (6 items), appraisal support (8 items) and self-esteem support (6 items) and belonging support (8 items). This indicates that the ISEL is valid in measuring the latent construct of social support in Indonesia. ISEL-Indonesia also meets the convergent validity criteria based on construct reliability calculations. The reliability of ISEL-Indonesia is also quite good, both when viewed as a unidimensional and multidimensional construct. This shows that the ISEL-Indonesia (28 items) has proven to be valid and reliable in measuring social support in the Indonesian adolescent population.

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